

GENESIS OF MODERN ARAB NOVEL

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Abstract. *The development of modern Arabic literature entered a new stage at the beginning of the 20th century. While poetry had traditionally been the leading genre in Arab culture, in the 20th century, the genre of the novel began to occupy a prominent place in literature. The emergence, development of the novel genre, and its establishment in Arabic literature are linked to the influence of Western literature, social, and political changes. This article will analyze the genesis of the modern Arab novel, its stages of development, main themes, and styles.*

Keywords: *prose, short story, poetry, novel, national heritage traditions, translated works.*

The novel represents the largest epic genre in terms of volume. It features numerous protagonists and characters with their own experiences and emotions. The novel is a type of prose genre. Initially, prose was stylistically weak, but over time, thanks to literary connections and translated works, the novel developed and reached stages of perfection. The novel illuminates life's problems and human attitudes towards them in the context of rapid civilizational development, while also encompassing historical, political, and social themes. It primarily addresses social and psychological issues.

A novel is a series of events narrated in the form of a long prose story, in which fictional or real characters and events are portrayed in a sequential narrative. It is considered the largest of prose genres in terms of length, number of characters, and variety of events. The novel emerged as a literary genre in Europe in the eighteenth century. The reader becomes immersed in its world, continuously experiencing the events. A skilled writer, however, can mislead the reader with certain truths while diverting attention from the actual truth. This surprises the reader by the end of the novel.

Indeed, in a truly artistically powerful novel, the writer, not revealing the idea of the work, but skillfully instilling it in the composition of the work through the art of artistic words, encourages the reader to think and draw conclusions.

The term "novel" is an abbreviation of the Italian word "novella" (derived from the plural form of the Latin word "novellus," which is a later variant of the word "novus" meaning "new"). Thus, this term, which is used today in many languages as a diminutive word, historically belonged to the original form.

There are several requirements for a novel, the most important of which are: the reality in the novel is built on the basis of plot development, characters, setting, style, storyline, and the space where events take place.

The novel is considered the largest type of story in terms of length, but length is not the only feature that distinguishes the novel from other genres. The novel represents a specific unit of time and environment, that is, it has a time scale that is typical for perception. This time scale can span a long period, but it can also be extended to encompass the age of the main character or the lives of subsequent generations.

Saudi writer Hanaa Hijazi, in her article "How Do You Benefit from Reading Novels?" published in Al-Arabiya, expressed the following thoughts: "Novels encourage you to experience

new emotions, their literary language expands your vocabulary, develops your imagination, and allows you to positively detach from reality. Novels are a creative mental system, and those who consider them useless miss out on enjoyment. I am amazed by people who do not sufficiently value novels, because it is through novels that we have become acquainted with the cultures, customs, histories, knowledge, and linguistic heritage of different peoples. Novels introduce you to problems you weren't aware of. Some novels contain profound and beautiful ideas that you cannot find in the books of philosophers."

In fact, during the first decades of the twentieth century, Arabic script held a firm position in Egypt. During this period, while the "Devon" group defended its ideas about poetry and innovation, Takha Khussein became a historian who boldly criticized traditional views on the history of literature. At that time, Egypt transformed into the center of literary activity for the entire Arab world, and Egyptian writers, like other Arab creators, dedicated their work to popularizing poetry, the Arabs' beloved art form.

When studying the formation of the novel in Arabic, it's important to consider that the adoption of this literary genre by young Arab writers occurred not only as a result of familiarity with Western fiction achievements but also because the novel's emergence in the Arab world was timely. This phenomenon corresponded to the needs and characteristics of the literature and readers of that era. However, the "readiness" in modern art was insufficient for introducing and establishing new forms and genres (whether in fiction or drama). This process required conscious efforts to develop their techniques, incorporate their unique artistry, and present them as reading material before they could become mainstream genres. High literature was still dominated by poetry. Mikhail Nuaymeh (1889-1988), an Arab-American critic who worked in the second decade of the 20th century, noted that at the beginning of the 20th century, it would have been beneficial to abandon excessive focus on poetry for the sake of future artistic experiments. The process of forming modern Arabic literature began by introducing Arab readers to new literature through translations of Western works. As with poetry, the initially translated novels were of the romantic genre: Hugo's "Les Misérables" was translated (through intermediaries) by the famous Egyptian poet Khafiz Ibrakhim at the beginning of the century, while Goethe's "The Sorrows of Young Werther" was translated from French by the poet and essayist Akhmad Khasan al-Zayyat.

In the twentieth century, al-Manfaluti's translations from French literature through intermediaries gained particular importance. His free translations of four famous works of French literature - Edmond Rostand's play "Cyrano de Bergerac," Alphonse Karr's novel "The Tille Sisters," and Bernardin de Saint-Pierre's novel "Paul and Virginia" - were quickly recognized not only in the Arab world but also in other countries, and generations have delighted in them. This was due not only to his fluent, precise, vivid, and pure Arabic style but also to the romantic nature of the works, which perfectly matched the romantic mood that was intensifying in the Arab world at the time.

Al-Manfaluti also attempted to create his own original work, albeit with less success, in the form of long stories that dealt with events that could serve as the basis for entire novels, mainly devoted to the difficulties and shortcomings of Arab society at the turn of the twentieth century.

This type of fiction, which incorporated critical social themes, was pioneered in America by Jubran Khalil Jubran (1883-1931), who published two collections of short and long stories in the first decade of the 20th century: "Nymphs of the Valley" ("Ara'is al-muruj," 1906) and "Spirits Rebellious" ("Al-arwah al-mutamarrida," 1908). These works were directed against inner

stagnation, shackles, lethargy, fanaticism, ignorance, and stagnation in the Arab world. In turn, the Egyptian Mustafa Lutfi al-Manfaluti focused entirely on describing the tragic aspects of the lives of the poor and how helplessness and immorality lead to misfortune. "Tears" ("Al-Abarat," 1916) is a collection of ten stories, six of which were translated and four were written directly by the author. The translated and original stories cover topics such as the consequences of corruption, physical weakness, betrayal, alcoholism and gambling, and the oppression and violence of those in power. They depict the dark sides of life, touch upon various aspects of love, and promote the values of loyalty, chastity, nobility, and self-sacrifice.

The first half of the twentieth century was a period that demanded more labor, displayed less boldness, and saw a slower adoption of the tools of quality fiction. Undoubtedly, these new forms would not have become the primary genres in modern Arabic literature without the earnest and dedicated efforts of several authors. They worked tirelessly to achieve this goal during the initial decades of the twentieth century. However, from the mid-century onwards, experimentation in the field of fiction became widespread, leading to a deeper understanding of the artistic foundations of these literary forms.

Egypt produced some of the most renowned novelists and short story writers in the modern Arab world, and over time became the center of modern Arabic fiction. Although readers in the Arab world seemed to have warmly received translations of European authors' literary works, many critics considered this phenomenon to pose a certain threat to morality and language. Concurrently, "other authors expressed their disapproval of the old genres of fiction, particularly tales about genies, giants, and spells, such as the stories in 'One Thousand and One Nights,' and emphasized that people had now abandoned these stories because they 'began to seek truth'. This is extremely significant. The genuine resistance to the introduction of new genres came from representatives of the old literary circle, who fought against the enormous changes that occurred in all aspects of literature in our time, and they ultimately surrendered".

Then Farakh Antun also worked productively in translation. Al-Muwailihi in "The Khadith of Isa ibn Khisham," and Khafiz Ibrakhim in "Nights of Satih," approached the forms of the hereditary genre in their narrative activities, which were recognized by great intellectuals as being in the form of maqama.

The title and dedication of Al-Muwailihi's book clearly show his connection to the ancient Arabic heritage and to the leaders of religious, social, and linguistic reforms who aimed to reform the revival of this heritage. He does not call his book a story or a novel, but rather "The Khadith of Isa ibn Khisham". The khadiths of Ibn Khisham mainly relied on the "Maqama" method. However, the difference between "The Khadiths and Maqams of Isa ibn Khisham" and the enlightened narratives before it is that, although it may seem weak, he attempted to find an internal connection between the chapters of his book.

It would not be a mistake if we unanimously acknowledge that the genre of the Arabic historical novel originated with Jurji Zaydan, as he presented a number of historical novels that included aspects of the narrative structure of Islamic history in the East and West. He is the author of historical novels such as "The Queen of Egypt Armanusa", "The Virgin Daughter of the Quraysh", "The Tragedy of Karbala", and "Al-Hajjaj ibn Yusuf". Each of Jurji Zaydan's novels contains two main elements: the first is a historical element based on historical events and characters, and the second is a fictional element based on the romantic relationship between two lovers.

In his novels, Farakh Antun attempted to emulate George Zaydan, who masterfully combined historical reality and love in his works. Antun wrote the novel "The New Jerusalem," which narrates the Arab conquest of Jerusalem during the reign of Caliph Umar. While it incorporates elements of love, these are considerably less prominent than the romantic elements found in George Zaydan's works. The educational novel aimed to reform education and society through social criticism, influenced by Western literature and targeted at the Egyptian intelligentsia. However, from the late 19th century until the national revolution of 1919, the trend of entertainment novels dominated. During this period, novels were not recognized by major intellectuals and writers, as the efforts of the intelligentsia were directed either towards political struggle or social reform.

We observe that the writer Khussein Khaykal does not use the term "novel" for his work "Zaynab" and instead refers to it as "Scenes" because the word "novel" is a new term in the language.

Conclusion. The genesis of the modern Arabic novel is distinguished by its encompassing of unique literary processes. The novel genre developed under the influence of Western literature on one hand, while maintaining connections to national heritage traditions on the other. Arabic novelists conducted artistic explorations while drawing upon global literary experiences. The new Arabic novel emerged as a result of close familiarity with literary connections and translated works. In the early forms of the Arabic novel, writers placed greater emphasis on socio-political themes.

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